

Supplementary material for 'Automated Assistance for Data Modelers: A Heuristics-based Natural Language Processing Approach'

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Description of modeling task 1 (Car Rental)

The current fleet of the car rental consists of cars, with a unique vehicle number recorded for each car. To determine the usage period of a car, the acquisition date is recorded for each car. Moreover, the acquisition price is also recorded for each car as well as the color. In addition, each car is described by a car type designation and its range. The car rental has several locations. Cars can be rented at exactly one of the rental locations. A name is assigned to each location. Employees of the car rental are assigned to exactly one rental location. At least one employee works at each location. All employees of the car rental company are assigned an alphanumeric personnel number and their first name and last name, date of birth and hire date are recorded. Customers of the car rental must be natural persons. When registering as customer, the first name, last name, date of birth as well as the date of registration are entered and a unique ID is assigned. For customers, the International Bank Account Number for delayed returns of cars is recorded. Customers of the car rental can rent any number of cars. A rental always refers to exactly one car. For a rental, the date of the rental and the due date are recorded in order to determine if a car is overdue. (228 words)

Description of modeling task 2 (Library)

The current stock of the university library consists of library items. Library items are described by a title and a year of publication. In addition, the first name and last name of the first author of the library item are recorded. There may be one or more copies of a library item. Each copy of a library item has a unique shelfmark. To determine the age of the library's holdings, the acquisition date is recorded for each copy. In order to be able to identify particularly valuable items, the acquisition price is also recorded for each copy. The university library has several different physical locations. Copies of library items can be found at exactly one of the university library's locations. A name is assigned to each location. Employees of the library are assigned to exactly one library location. At least one employee works at each location. All employees of the library are assigned an alphanumeric personnel number and their first name and last name, date of birth and hire date are recorded. Users of the library must be natural persons. When registering as user, the first name, last name, date of birth as well as the date of registration are entered and a unique alphanumeric user name is assigned. Users of the university library can borrow any number of copies of library items. A loan always refers to exactly one copy. For a loan, the date of the loan and the due date are recorded in order to be able to determine if the loan is overdue. (257 words)

Description of modeling task 3 (Project Structure)

Each programmer has a name, address and date of birth. Each project has a name, budget, starting date and ending date. A programming language has a name and a platform. A consultant may supervise many projects. A consultant has a name, address and date of birth. A project can be supervised by only one consultant. A programmer works in at most two projects. At least one programmer works on a project. A programmer uses at least on programming language. In a project, exactly one programmer language is used. (88 words)

Description of modeling task 4 (Department Structure)

A company is organized into departments. Each department has a number, a name and a manager. For each manager, a start date is stored. A department may have several locations. A location is identified by a unique name. A department controls a number of projects. Each project has a unique name, a unique number and a single location. Each employee has a name, SSN, address, salary, gender and birth date. An employee is assigned to one department. However each employee may work on several projects, which are not necessarily controlled by the same department. Each project needs some parts supplied by some suppliers. A supplier has a unique name, a contact person's first and last name and an address are assigned. A part is described by a unique part number, a description and a cost. *(135 words)*

Description of modeling task 5 (Car Registration)

Each person is described by a social service number. Each person also has a name, address, number of the driver's license, and date of birth. A person can own one or more cars. In addition, the same car can be owned by more than one person. Cars are identified by their VIN. Each car also has a registered plate number which consists of the state that issued it, the actual number, and what type of plate. All cars must have a valid insurance policy. An insurance policy is identified by a vehicle registration number and an expiry date. *(98 words)*